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REVIEW ON CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES WITH HETEROCYCLIC LIGANDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims on Characterization and antimicrobial activities of some transition metal complexes with their heterocyclic ligands. It is better to elucidate structure of a new compound based on the experimental evidence or observation (eg IR, NMR etc) than predicting it based on the proposed reaction mechanism. The mechanism may or may not be exact route or the predicted product may or may not be the only final product predicted. Many heterocyclic ligands show good antimicrobial activities and these activities increase very much when they form complexes with metal. This shows that antimicrobial activities of metal complexes depend more on the metal center itself in addition to the structure of ligands and on the geometry around the metal ion.

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INTRODUCTION

Like all sciences, chemistry involves two parallel processes, experimentation and explanation. Explanations are built on the results of experiments and then using those explanations additional experiments are designed to further test the explanation and also provide new information [1]. The synthetic chemist is not only concerned with the preparation of new compounds; he often seeks new and better methods for preparing compounds that have been known to many years.

Usually the first method used for the preparation of a compound is inefficient or inconvenient. Thus the motive for seeking a better synthetic procedure is obvious. There are many inorganic compounds that might change from laboratory curiosities to commercially important chemicals if practical synthesis were found for them [2]. Thus good synthetic techniques require due attention to the purity of reagents and solvents. Since repeatability is an important part of experimental work, impurities that may affect the outcome of a reaction must be eliminated and when choosing a solvent, the air and moisture-sensitivity of reagents should be considered. Different heterocyclic compounds including monocyclic and fused ring systems have been known, are being synthesized, complexed with metals and their applications are studied. Complexation with metals is mainly due to the presence of donor atoms [3].

Schiff's bases form stable complexes with metals that perform an important role in biological systems. Transition metal Schiff base complexes have many applications in the area of antitumoral, antiviral and antibacterial activity as well as mimetic systems for enzyme models. The ability of transition metal Schiff base complexes, especially Ni(II), Cu(II), Co(II) salicylaldehydes to act as neutral donor ligands toward tin(IV)halides, organotin(IV) halides, pseudo-halides and tin(II) halides as acceptors is well documented [4].

When an aldehyde or a ketone is condensed with a primary amine, a Schiff base is produced, which is a compound containing azomethine group, R-C=N- [5,6] reported the synthesis and magnetic studies on schiff base complexes of copper (II). [7] reported the synthesis and characterization of Mn (II), Co (II) and Cu (II) complexes with a novel schiff base ligand derived from 2,2'-bis(p-methoxyphenylamine) and salicylic aldehyde. Transition metal schiff base complexes have been found to play a vital role in medicine, biological systems and industries.

The field of medicine has witnessed an increase in the number of complexes with therapeutic value, for example, Cobalt(III) Schiff base complexes are potential antiviral agents, cis dichloro di amine platinum (II) is an anti-cancer agent and copper (II) schiff base complex is an anti-tubercular agent (Lippard, 1994; Bleomycin and Reed, 1996). The use of atom transfer radical cyclisation mediated by copper (II) schiff base complexes to furnish nitrogen heterocycles most of which are biologically active molecules and also the use of copper schiff base catalyst in carbon based radical cyclisation reactions were recently investigated [8]. The complex compound formed by schiff base derived from benzoin and 2-amino benzoic acid with cobalt (II) salt has been reported [9].

Compounds classified as heterocyclic probably constitute the largest and most varied family of organic compounds. After all, every carbocyclic compound, regardless of structure and functionality may in principle be converted into a collection of heterocyclic analogs by replacing one or more of the ring carbon atoms with a different element. Even if we restrict our consideration to oxygen, nitrogen and sulfur (the most common heterocyclic elements), the permutations and combinations of such a replacement are numerous. Transition metal complexes containing heterocyclic compounds have been of considerable interest in terms of structural chemistry, catalysis and biological functions. The field has undergone spectacular growth due to the synthesis of multidentate ligands from heterocyclic compounds to synthesize chelates with metal ions [10].

There are a number of multidentate ligands that play important roles in coordination chemistry and catalyst designing. The degree of interaction between the metal center and the neutral ligand atom can exert a profound influence on the reactivity of the resulting complexes. A large number of multidentate ligands have been synthesized and investigated for their metal binding character [11-14]. The aim of this review is to grasp concept of characterization and antimicrobial activity of transition metal complexes with heterocyclic ligand by taking some of the first series transition metals.

Nickel (II) Complexes (Ni^{2+} , d^8)

The DNA binding ability of inert chiral transition metal complexes has attracted considerable interest. Recent studies have shown that a variety of transition metal complexes have significant potential as probes for sequence- and structure-specific DNA binding. Significant attention has centered upon metal complexes capable of binding DNA by intercalation, and, in particular, due to their luminescent properties and strong DNA binding affinity. Replacement of the hydrogen-bonded base pairing of natural DNA by alternative base pairing modes is expected to lead not only to expansion of the genetic alphabet but to novel DNA structures and functions based on the controlled and periodic spacing of the building blocks along the helix axis [15].

In the majority of the complexes studied the metal ion serves as the oxidation agent while the ligand is responsible for DNA recognition. The modes of recognition are primarily based upon intercalation, groove-binding and hydrogen-bonding interactions. Site-specific DNA modification has also been observed for transition complexes that are covalently linked to DNA-binding proteins. In contrast, platinum chemotherapeutic agents such as cis-Pt(NH₃)₂Cl₂ (cis-platin) interact specifically with duplex DNA by forming covalent bonds between the platinum metal center and N7 of guanine. The mode of action of cis-platin is believed to involve the replacement of the two labile chloride ions with guanine resulting in intra strand cross-links. Nickel macrocyclic complexes that possess vacant or labile coordination sites may also ligate to DNA bases, and effect site-specific reactions with DNA.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Characterization Methods

Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)

Quantitative determination of metal content of complexes can be determined by Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). It is an analytical technique that measures the concentrations of elements. It is commonly used for determining the concentration of a particular metal element within a sample. AAS can be used to analyze the concentration of over 62 different metals in a solution. AAS determines the presence of metals in liquid samples. Metals include Ni, Fe, Cu,

Al, Pb, Ca, Zn, Cd and many more. Atomic absorption is so sensitive that it can measure down to parts per billion of a gram (g dm^{-3}) in a sample. Typical concentrations range in the low mg/L range.

In their elemental form, metals will absorb ultraviolet light when they are excited by heat. Each metal has a characteristic wavelength that will be absorbed. The AAS instrument looks for a particular metal by focusing a beam of UV light at a specific wavelength through a flame and into a detector. The sample of interest is aspirated into the flame. If that metal is present in the sample, it will absorb some of the light, thus reducing its intensity. The instrument measures the change in intensity. A computer data system converts the change in intensity into an absorbance [16]. The metal contents in the complexes can be determined spectroscopically using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) by using the formula:

$$M(\%) = \text{Concentration (PPm)} \times \frac{\text{volume diluted to}}{\text{mass of sample taken}} \times \frac{100}{1000}$$

Electronic spectral and magnetic properties

The perception of color by the human eye results from the action of electromagnetic radiation with wavelengths occupying the range from about 400 to 780nm on the optical nerve. Simultaneous action of the wavelengths in the entire visible range causes the perception of white, while the narrow bands of radiation, or their combinations, which remain in the spectrum after extraction of some special bands, cause the perception of color. If a coordination compound absorbs light of one color, we see the complement of that color. For example, the deep blue color of aqueous solution of Cu(II) compound, containing the ion $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ as the result of absorption of light 585 - 620 nm. Note that the color absorbed is orange and thus it is a complementary color of blue. In general for many coordination compounds, the electronic absorption spectrum provides a convenient method for determining the magnitude of the effect of ligands on the d-orbitals of the metal and it helps us to study this effect for coordination compounds of any geometry [17].

In the Uv-Vis spectroscopy, the transitions that result in the absorption of electromagnetic radiation in this region of spectrum (190nm to 800nm) are transitions between electronic energy levels. As a molecule absorbs energy, an electron is promoted from the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). The energy differences between electronic levels in most molecules vary from 125 to 650 kJ/mole. The wavelength, λ , is related to this energy difference, ΔE , by the equation:

$$\Delta E = h\nu = hc/\lambda$$

Where $h = 6.63 \times 10^{-34} \text{Js}^{-1}$ is Planks constant and ν is the frequency of the light.

If the light of intensity I_0 at a given wavelength passes through a solution containing a species that absorbs light, the light emerges with intensity I ($I < I_0$), then the light absorbed may be described by the Beer-Lambert equation:

$$\text{Log}(I_0/I) = A = \epsilon lc,$$

Where A = absorbance, ϵ = molar absorptivity l = path length through solution (cm).

The Uv-Vis spectrum is usually recorded as a plot of absorbance (A) versus wavelength (nm). It is then customary to re plot the data with either ϵ or $\log \epsilon$ plotted on the ordinate and wavelength plotted on the abscissa. UV absorbances are generally broad because vibrational and rotational energy levels are superimposed on top of the electronic levels.

The choice of solvent to be used in the ultraviolet spectroscopy is quite important. The first criterion for a good solvent is that it should not absorb ultraviolet radiation in the same region as the substance whose spectrum is being determined. Usually solvents that do not contain conjugated systems are most suitable for this purpose, although they vary as to the shortest wavelength at which they remain transparent to ultraviolet radiation.

A second criterion for a good solvent is its effect on the fine structure of an absorption band. A non-polar solvent is not hydrogen bonded with the solute and the spectrum of the solute closely approximates the spectrum that would be produced in the gaseous phase, where fine structure is often observed. In a polar solvent, the hydrogen bonding forms a solute-solvent complex, and the fine structure may disappear.

A third criterion for a good solvent is its ability to influence the wavelength of UV light that will be absorbed via stabilization of either the ground or the excited state. Polar solvents do not form hydrogen bonds as readily with the excited states of the polar molecules as with their ground states, and these polar solvents increase the energies of electronic transitions in the molecules. Polar solvents shift transitions of the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ type to shorter wavelengths. On the other hand, in some cases the excited states may form stronger hydrogen bonds than the corresponding ground states. In such a case, a polar solvent shifts absorption to longer wavelength, since the energy of the electronic transition is decreased. Polar solvents shift $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ type to longer wavelengths. Although the absorption of UV radiation results from the excitation of electrons from ground to excited states, the nuclei that hold the electrons together in bonds play an important role in determining which wavelengths of radiation are absorbed. The nuclei determine the strength with which the electrons are bound and thus influence the energy spacing between ground and excited states. Hence the characteristic energy of a transition and the wavelength of radiation absorbed are properties of a group of atoms rather than of electrons themselves. The group of atoms producing such absorption is called a chromophore.

Charge transfer transitions are generally intense compared with ligand filled transitions, i.e., charge transfer gives rise to intense absorptions whereas d-d bands are much weaker. The excitation of a molecule from its electronic ground state to an electronic excited state corresponds to absorption of light in the near-infrared, visible or ultraviolet regions of the spectrum. For transition metal complexes, the absorption bands in the first two of these regions (infrared and visible) are relatively weak and are associated with transitions largely localized on the metal atom. The ultraviolet bands are intense and they are associated with the transfer of an electron from one atom to another and so are called charge-transfer bands. The spectra of transition metal complexes depend on the transition of unpaired electrons from the ground state to an excited state. Transitions may occur between the split d-levels of the central atom, giving rise to the d-d or ligand field spectra. The spectra region where these bands occur spans the near infra-red, visible and UV. Most of the transition metal complexes are coloured due to d-d transitions in the visible region. The atomic overlap in metal-ligand bonds allows d electrons to penetrate from the central atom to the ligand, and vice versa. The transitions are affected by the effect of ligands on the energies of the d orbital of the metal ions. Since octahedral, square-planar and tetrahedral fields cause splitting of d orbitals in different ways, the geometry will have a pronounced effect on the d-d transitions in a metal complex. Thus spectral data of transition metals provide useful information about the structure of complexes [18].

For example, the Ni(II) ion has d^8 outer electron configuration which gives rise to the triplet and singlet terms. In octahedral and slightly tetragonally distorted octahedral fields, two unpaired electrons are present; the ground state makes no orbital contribution to the magnetic moment so that these moments are expected to be not greatly different from the spin only moment (2.83 BM). In tetrahedral field, two unpaired electrons are present; there is also orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. Thus, the magnetic moments are expected to be well in excess of the spin only value, and typically lie in the range of 3.2-4.0 BM. Take Ni(II) as example for simplicity for all characterization methods to be explained next to this.

Electronic spectral and magnetic properties of tetrahedral Ni(II) complexes

For regular or nearly regular tetrahedral complexes there are characteristic spectral and magnetic properties. The tetrahedral Ni(II) complexes with ${}^3T_1(F)$ ground state generally exhibit four transitions: ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3A_2$, ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow 1E$, ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ and ${}^3T_2 \rightarrow {}^1T_1$. The band ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ is a strong band of high intensity when compared with others. The transition from the ground ${}^3T_1(F)$ state to the ${}^3T_1(P)$ state occurs in the visible region ($\sim 15,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and is relatively strong ($\epsilon \approx 102$) compared to the corresponding ${}^3A_2 \rightarrow {}^3T_1$ transition in octahedral complexes. Thus tetrahedral complexes are generally strongly colored and tend to be blue or green unless the ligands also have absorption bands in the visible region. Because the ground state ${}^3T_1(F)$ has much inherent orbital angular momentum, the magnetic moments of truly tetrahedral Ni(II) should be about 4.2 BM at room temperature. However, even slight distortions reduce this markedly (by splitting the orbital degeneracy). Thus fairly regular tetrahedral complexes have moments of 3.5 - 4.0 BM, for the more distorted ones the moments are 3.0 - 3.5 BM [19]. In tetrahedral fields the outer electronic configuration becomes $e^4 t_2^4$. Three spin allowed transition are possible from the 3T_1 ground state. These absorption bands are shifted towards the infrared as compared to the octahedral bands.

The absorption bands of tetrahedral complexes differ in being more intense due to the absence of a center of symmetry in the complex. Moreover, the spectra show a very broadband. The absorption band, approximately at $15,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the ${}^3T_1(F)$ to $T_1(P)$ transition and the one at $7,000\text{-}8,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the $T_1(F)$ to A_2 transition. The near infrared band around 700 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3A_2$ transition; the lowest energy band, corresponding to the ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2$ transition. Since the ground term 3T_1 in the tetrahedral nickel(II) complex is orbitally degenerate, the magnetic moment is expected to be raised considerably over the spin only value through orbital contribution. The experimental values lie within the range of 3.2-4.1 BM. Although octahedral and high spin tetrahedral complexes have moments between 2.83 and 3.4 BM, theoretically, regular tetrahedral complexes with four identical ligands have magnetic moment between 3.5 and 4.2 BM [20].

Electronic spectral and magnetic properties of square planar Ni(II) complexes

For the vast majority of four coordinated Ni(II) complexes containing strong field ligands, square planar geometry is preferred. Square planar complexes of Ni(II) are thus invariably diamagnetic. They are frequently red, yellow or brown owing to the presence of the absorption band of medium intensity ($\epsilon \approx 60$) in the range 450-600 nm. Square planar Ni(II) complexes don't have any absorption band below $10,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, due to large crystal field splitting. Hence they can be clearly distinguished from octahedral and tetrahedral complexes. [20].

Ni(II) forms a large number of square planar complexes. The planar configuration is stabilized by strong nickel-ligand covalent bonding (both- σ and π -bonding). The electronic ground state of a planar complex may be either $e^4_g a_1g^2 b_2g^2$, i.e., a spin singlet state $1A_1g$, or $e^4_g a_1g^2 b_2g^1 b_1g^1$, i.e., or a spin triplet state $3A_2g$ and an excited state $1A_2g$. The low spin state is favored if the separation between the dx^2-y^2 and dxy orbitals is more than $10,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Their spectra frequently consist of a strong ($\epsilon=50-5001\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$) band around $15,000-23,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a second band in the range $23,000-27,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These bands are commonly assigned to the transitions $1A_1g \rightarrow 1A_2g(b_2g \rightarrow b_1g)$ and $1A_1g \rightarrow 1B_1g(a_1g \rightarrow b_1g)$. A further weaker band is sometimes observed in the $11,000-15,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. The major difference between the spectra of square planar complexes and those of octahedral or tetrahedral complexes is the absence of any bands below $10,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Planar complexes are all diamagnetic; no unique interpretation of the spectra is yet possible [22]. In short, all truly square planar complexes of nickel(II) are of the low-spin(diamagnetic) type.

Electronic spectral and magnetic properties of Octahedral Ni(II) complexes

The maximum coordination number of Nickel(II) is 6. Nickel(II) complexes with six coordination number are always high spin complexes having either regular or distorted octahedral geometry. The 3F ground term split in an octahedral field giving rise to the triple terms. Octahedral Ni(II) complexes have 3A_2g ground state. This type of complexes is expected to have three spin-allowed transitions $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^3T_2g$, $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^3T_1g(P)$ and $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^3T_1g(F)$ in the ranges of $7000-13000$, $11000-20000$ and $19000-27000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. On the other hand, the $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^1E_g$ band in region the $11,000-15,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^3T_1g(F)$ band in to the $17,000-22,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Transitions to spin singlet levels are sometimes observable. Two spin forbidden transitions are also possible; $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^1E_g$ and $^3A_2g \rightarrow ^1T_2g$. Octahedral Ni(II) complexes have two unpaired electrons and depending on the orbital angular momentum contribution they possess magnetic moments ranging from 2.9 to 3.4 BM. From both a simple d-orbital splitting and the energy level diagrams, it follows that all of them have two unpaired electrons, and this is found always to be the case for the magnetic moments to have this range value. There are a few complexes which are both diamagnetic and 6-coordinates, the most thoroughly studied of this is the nickel(II) iodide-o-phenylenebismethylarsine complex $Ni_2(\text{diars})_2$. So octahedral nickel(II) complexes have relatively simple magnetic behavior and it can be concluded that regular octahedral complexes of nickel(II) are always paramagnetic. [20].

Magnetic susceptibility (χ_m)

When a substance is placed in an external magnetic field, the substance will produce its own magnetic field. If the substance is paramagnetic, this field adds to the applied field. If the substance is diamagnetic, this field subtracts from the main field. This contribution to the external magnetic field is known as the magnetic susceptibility (χ_m) of the substance. χ_m is positive for the paramagnetic material ($\chi_m > 0$), and the magnetic field is strengthened by the presence of the material and it is negative for the diamagnetic material ($\chi_m < 0$), and the magnetic field is weakened in the presence of the material. The magnetic susceptibilities of paramagnetic and diamagnetic materials are generally extremely small. For paramagnetic complexes, the experimental magnetic moments can be obtained using the following formula;

$$\chi_M = \chi_g \times M.Wt.$$

Where, χ_M _ molar magnetic susceptibility ($\text{cm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}$), χ_g _ gram magnetic susceptibility ($\text{cm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$), M.Wt. (g mol^{-1}).

The χ_M is subjected to diamagnetic correction using Pascal constants to obtain corrected magnetic susceptibility (χ_M^{corr}), the magnetic moment can finally be calculated as;

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84(\chi_M^{\text{corr}} \cdot T)^{1/2}$$

Where, μ_{eff} = magnetic moment and T = temperature in K.

Then from the effective magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) obtained, the number of unpaired electrons can be calculated using the relation;

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = [n(n+2)]^{1/2}$$

Where, n = number of unpaired electrons.

IR (FTIR) Spectra

Infrared (IR) radiation is electromagnetic radiation of a wavelength longer than that of visible light (400 to 800nm), but shorter than that of micro waves (longer than 1mm). The name means "below red" (from the latin infra, "below"), red being the color of visible light of longest wavelength. IR covers 12500 to 50 cm^{-1} in the electromagnetic spectrum. The IR region is divided in to three as near IR ($12500-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), middle IR ($4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and far IR ($400-50\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Of these, middle IR is useful because almost all compounds having covalent bonds whether organic or inorganic absorb various frequencies of electromagnetic radiation in the infrared region of electromagnetic spectrum and hence are studied in this region.

As with other types of energy absorption, molecules are excited to a higher energy state when they absorb IR radiation. A molecule absorbs only selected frequencies (energies) of infrared radiation. The absorption of IR corresponds to energy changes on the order of 8 to 40 kJ/mole. Radiation energies associated with this part are not large enough to excite electrons, but corresponds to the range encompassing the stretching and bending vibrational frequencies of the bonds in most covalent molecules. IR spectra may be obtained from samples in all phases (liquid, solid or gaseous). Liquids are usually examined as a thin film sandwiched between two polished salt plates (note that glass absorbs IR, whereas NaCl is transparent). If solvents are used to dissolve solids, care must be taken to avoid obscuring important spectral regions by solvent absorption. Perchlorated solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, and tetrachloroethene are commonly used. Alternatively solids may be incorporated in a thin KBr disk, prepared under high pressure, or mixed with a little non-volatile liquid and ground to a paste (or a mull) that is smeared between salt plates.

NMR Spectra

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is an absorption spectroscopy involving the absorption of radio frequency EM waves. The energy associated with a photon in the radio frequencies is extremely small compared to IR frequencies. NMR involves changes in the spin state of the nucleus of an atom. Not all nuclei display spin. In order to display spin, a nucleus must have an odd number of protons or neutrons. Hydrogen has one proton, so displays spin (^1H or proton display spin are isotopes of common elements (deuterium is an isotope of hydrogen). The most common are ^{13}C , ^{19}F , ^{15}N and ^{29}Si . An atom with spin has a non-zero spin quantum number, I . For most nuclei of interest the spin quantum number is $\frac{1}{2}$. Deuterium and Nitrogen 15 have spin quantum numbers of 1. The number of spin states possible for a nucleus is given by $2I+1$. The nucleus can be thought of as a magnet, and in the absence of a magnetic field these tiny magnets are randomly arranged in a sample with no preferred direction for the magnetic moment vectors. Application of a radiofrequency EM wave to such a sample has no effect, i.e. there is no absorption. There is no absorption because the system cannot tell the difference between magnetic vectors pointing up or down or any other direction since these directions have no reference base. This is analogous to a guitar string which is not constrained or two atoms which are not bonded in IR. In the absence of constraints there is no perceptible absorption.

If a strong magnetic field is applied to the nuclei, they can tell the difference between alignments in the direction of the applied magnetic field and opposed to the applied magnetic field. In NMR the constraint which leads to quantized transitions is applied by the spectrometer. Because of this the frequency of absorption varies with the applied magnetic field and there is no absolute frequency or wavelength for a given absorption. NMR spectra are not plotted as absorption versus wave number as IR spectra are; plotted as absorption versus chemical shift, δ . The chemical shift for proton NMR is the difference between the frequency of absorption of the sample and a standard, tetramethylsilane (TMS) normalized by the frequency of absorption of TMS.

The strength of an IR magnitude of the magnetogyric ration, g , i.e. how large the magnetic dipole moment is. The absorption in IR is also proportional to the concentration of the absorbing bond. NMR depends on the presence of specific isotopes. In considering the strength of an NMR absorption band we consider the "natural abundance" of these isotopes. For example, 99.98 percent of hydrogen atoms are ^1H , and 0.0156 percent is deuterium, ^2H . The magnetogyric ratio for hydrogen is 26,700 while for deuterium is 4,100. This means that proton NMR (^1H) results in 100 times the signal as deuterium if a sample contains natural abundance hydrogen.

A similar comparison shows that proton NMR absorption is about 50 times stronger than ^{13}C NMR (natural abundance of ^{13}C is about 1%). An NMR absorption peak for a given nucleus is directly proportional to the number of these atoms in a sample. In the ^1H NMR spectra the number of signals indicates the number of different types of protons and the integration specifies the ratios of number of protons. These can help in indicating molecular formula. Chemical shifts indicate the types of protons and functional groups present.

Numbers to know (All +1) : 1ppm-Aliphatic protons:

: 2ppm	Alyllic protons
: 3ppm	Aliphatic protons with one hetroatom attached protons
: 6ppm	Alkene protons
: 7ppm	Aromatic protons
: 10ppm	Aldehyde protons
: 12ppm	Acid

Most NMR spectra are recorded for compounds dissolved in a solvent. Therefore, signals will be observed for the solvent and this must be accounted for in solving spectral problems. To avoid spectra dominated by the solvent signal, most ^1H NMR spectra are recorded in a deuterated solvent. However, deuteration is not 100%, so signals for the residual protons are observed. In chloroform solvent (CDCl_3), this corresponds to CHCl_3 , so a singlet signal is observed at 7.26 ppm. For methanol solvent, this corresponds to $\text{CH}_2\text{D}_2\text{O}$, so a 1:2:3:2:1 pentet signal is observed at 3.31 ppm. (Recall that deuterium has a spin quantum number (I) of 1, so n deuterium atoms will split a proton signal into $2In+1$ lines). The same solvents are used for ^{13}C NMR spectra, so the same rules also apply here about splitting patterns.

It used to be common practice to add Me_4Si , or related compounds, as an internal reference standard for ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra with the proton signal occurring at 0.0 ppm and the carbon signal occurring at 0.0 ppm in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum. However, modern spectrometers can lock on solvent signals, so addition of internal reference standards is not usually required.

Antimicrobial activities

Antimicrobial activities of heterocyclic ligands

Heterocyclic compounds are pharmacologically most important among organic compounds. These compounds possess versatile type of biological activities; some of these are well known for their anticancer, antitubercular, antibacterial, antifungal, anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory, antihypertensive activities, antiulcer, analgesic, and antiproliferative activities as well as inhibitory effects for thymidylate synthase. [22]. Among all these activities of heterocyclic compounds, antimicrobial activity of thiazolidinones and oxazolidinones was reviewed.

Antimicrobial activities of thiazolidinones

Thiazolidinones are derivatives of thiazolidine and they also constitute an important group of heterocyclic compounds. Thiazolidinones, with a carbonyl group in positions 2,4 or just 4-have been subject of extensive study in the recent past and literature surveys show that thiazolidin-4-one are important compounds due to their broad range of biological activities. 4-Thiazolidinones substituted in the 2-position, its derivatives and analogues exhibit unusually high in vitro activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [9, 23].

Biological activities of thiosemicarbazones are related to their abilities to form complex with metal cations, by bonding through the sulfur and azomethine nitrogen atoms. Several works demonstrate their activity against extracellular protozoan as *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Trichomonas vaginalis*, *T. cruzi* and other parasites. 4-Thiazolidinones play a vital role due to their wide range of biological activities and industrial importance. 4-Thiazolidinones are always being an attraction point for researchers because of its efficiency towards various pharmacological usages. The derivatives of 4-thiazolidinone nucleus have occupied a unique place in the field of medicinal chemistry due to wide range of biological activities like antibacterial, antitubercular, anticancer, anticonvulsant and antifungal. They have interesting activity profiles mainly COX-1 inhibitors, inhibitors of bacterial enzyme, nucleoside inhibitors of HIV and antihistaminic agents. Recent studies on molecular modification revealed that, dismantling of the imidazole nucleus leading to the design of new 1,3-thiazolidin-4-one derivatives, maintained the molecular requirements for enzyme inhibition [24].

A literature search revealed that, 4-thiazolidinone derivatives may exhibit antibacterial, antituberculosis, antiviral and anticancer properties. 4-thiazolidinones may also be considered as phosphate bioisosteres and therefore inhibit the bacterial enzyme which is involved in the biosynthesis of peptidoglycan layer of the cell wall. In addition, some thiazolidinones were recently reported as novel inhibitors of mycobacterial rhamnose synthase [25].

Antimicrobial activities oxazolidinones

Oxazolidinones are mainly used as antimicrobials pharmaceutically. Linezolid is the first oxazolidinone commercialized worldwide for treatment against multi-drug resistant gram positive infections. However, some linezolid resistant enterococci isolates have been recently isolated after intensive linezolid therapy and in therefore there appears, a need for second generation oxazolidinones with improved drug effectiveness with Gram positive bacteria. Some of the most important oxazolidinones are the last generation of antibiotics exhibiting good activity against multiple-resistant gram positive pathogens, including *penicillin-resistant streptococci*, *vancomycin-resistant enterococci* and super bugs such as *methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). These antibiotics are considered as a choice of last resort where every other antibiotic therapy has failed. The antibacterial effect of oxazolidinones is by working as protein synthesis inhibitors, targeting an early step involving the binding of N-formylmethionyl-tRNA to the ribosome. Examples of antibiotic oxazolidinones include:

- Linezolid, which is available for intravenous administration and also has the advantage of having excellent oral bioavailability.
- Posizolid, which appears to have excellent, targeted bactericidal activity against all common gram-positive bacteria, regardless of resistance to other classes of antibiotics.

The knowledge of antibacterial activity of natural products has led to the invention of antibiotics such as penicillins, tetracyclins, vancomycin and macrolides, etc. In addition to this, oxazolidinones have a unique mechanism of action and do not show cross-resistance with existing resistance mechanisms in bacteria [26]

Antimicrobial activity of some transition metal complexes

Coordination compounds are of great importance in biological systems. For example, chlorophyll is a coordination compound of magnesium, haemoglobin is a coordination compound of iron and vitamin B₁₂ is a coordination compound of cobalt. Coordination compounds, with bonds between a central metal atom and surrounding ligands, play critical roles in biology, biochemistry and medicine, controlling the structure and function of many enzymes and their metabolism. They play similarly vital roles in many industrial processes and in the development of new materials with specifically designed properties. Thus synthesis and study of such complexes is very important. Many studies concerning the relationship between metal ions and the bioactivity of drugs have been a subject of great interest [27]. A number of known biochemical reactions which are catalysed by enzymes contain metal ions such as Zn, Co, Mo etc. Many metal chelates which have been proved to be more carcinostatic than the unchelated drugs and similarly, many antibacterial drugs when are complexed/ chelated, their bioactivity is effectively altered

Ability of inert chiral transition metal complexes in binding DNA has also attracted considerable interest. Variety of transition metal complexes has significant potential as probes for sequence and structure-specific DNA binding. Significant attention has centered upon metal complexes capable of binding DNA by intercalation, and, in particular, due to their luminescent properties and strong DNA binding affinity. Replacement of the hydrogen-bonded base pairing of natural DNA by alternative base pairing modes is expected to lead not only to expansion of the genetic alphabet but to novel DNA structures and functions based on the controlled and periodic spacing of the building blocks along the helix axis. Nickel macrocyclic complexes that possess vacant or labile coordination sites are known to ligate to DNA bases, and effect site-specific reactions with DNA [28].

Semicarbazones are among the most relevant nitrogen-oxygen donor ligands. A good deal of work has been reported on the preparation and structural investigation of semicarbazones and their complexes. This is due partially to their capability of acting as multidentate, NO, NNO and ONNO donors with the formation of either mono- or bi- or polynuclear complexes. In addition thio- and semicarbazones possess a wide range of bioactivities, and their chemistry and pharmacological applications have been extensively investigated. Polymer complexes have also been given a great deal of attention in recent years. Polyvinyl alcohol (ethanol homopolymer) which considered as moderate adhesive is a water soluble resin. PVA is a polymer with exceptional properties such as water solubility, biodegradability, biocompatibility, non-toxicity and non-carcinogenicity that possesses the capability to form hydrogels by chemical or physical methods. Its fields of applicability were widely broadened during the later years due to the development of medicine [29].

The PVA ligand is biologically active and its activity may arise from the hydroxyl groups which may play an important role in the antibacterial activity. The synthesized compounds were found to be more toxic compared with their parent PVA ligand against the same micro-organism and under the identical experimental conditions. The increase in biological activity of the metal chelates may be due to the effect of the metal ion on the normal cell process. A possible mode of toxicity increase may be considered in the light of Tweedy's chelation theory. Chelation considerably reduce the polarity of the metal ion because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor group and possible p-electron delocalization within the whole chelate ring system that is formed during coordination. Such chelation could enhance the lipophilic character of the central metal atom and hence increasing the hydrophobic character and lipo solubility of the complex favoring its permeation through the lipid layers of the cell membrane. This enhances the rate of uptake/entrance and thus the antimicrobial activity of the testing compounds [30].

Accordingly, they reported that antimicrobial activity of the complexes can be referred to the increase of their lipophilic character which in turn deactivates enzymes responsible for respiration processes and probably other cellular enzymes, which play a vital role in various metabolic pathways of the tested microorganisms [31].

Antimicrobial activity of copper complexes

It is well known that the derivatives of thiosemicarbazones possess the antibacterial activity. In addition, there are many studies that show the antimicrobial activity of copper(II) complexes with these ligands. Common anti-bacterial agents have been also used as ligands to complex with copper ions. It was noticed that the antimicrobial activity against *M. Smegmatis* of a metal ion complex in comparison to free ciprofloxacin, a bacterial gyrase inhibitor, increased three times. It may result from facilitated diffusion of the drug through the cell membranes, presumably by an increase in the lipophilicity of the drug. The activity against *Streptococcus* can also be influenced by the slow release of the ligands inside the bacterial cell. This was noticed with the copper complex of isoniazide and ethambutol. It seems that intercellular reduction of Cu(II) into Cu(I) can activate the oxygen which is toxic for bacteria. Moreover, a copper(II) complex of sulfacetamide, (N-[4-(amino-phenyl)sulfonil]acetamide), has been intensively used in treatment of ophthalmic and dermatologic infections. Further studies of the copper(II) complexes of sulfacetamide and sulfanilamide and sulfisoxazole have showed promising results [32].

In general, sulfonamide copper(II) complexes show antimicrobial activity against both types, Gram(+) (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*) and Gram(-) (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). More often it shows slightly higher activity against Gram(-) bacteria. The copper(II) complexes of benzimidazoles have not only shown antibacterial activity against *S. epidermidis* but also some strong activity was found against fungi. In addition, complexes of thiabendazole appeared to be active. Moreover, antifungal activity against *Aspergillus* sp. and *Penicillium* sp. Was also found for a copper(II) complex of p-amino acetophenone benzoylhydrazone [33].

Antimicrobial activity of cobalt complexes

Various Co(III) complexes have been reported with antimicrobial activities. For instance, a Co(III) complex of the known antiulcer drug famotidine turned out to have greater antimicrobial activity against *E. coli* and *M. lysodeikticus* than the metal free drug. The pyrazine-2,3-dicarboxylate complexes of 1,10-phenanthroline and alkyl diamines have recently shown activity against Gram(+) and Gram(-) bacterial strains and fungi *C. albicans*. The cobalt(II) complexes of hinikitiol, 4-isopropyltropolone, appeared to be active, in comparison to copper(II) complexes. Interesting biological properties have been found in the series of metal(II) oxinates of the derivative of sulfonohydrazide, belonging to the group of sulfonamides. The octahedral cobalt complex possessed good activity against both Gram(+) and Gram(-) bacterial strains but not higher than the free ligand alone. Cobalt(II) complexes not only show antimicrobial but also antifungal activities. The complex of the imidazole-2-carbaldehyde semicarbazone turned out to be active against the yeasts *S. cerevisiae* and *C. tropicalis*. Activity was most noticeable against such phytopathogenic fungi as *Alternaria* or *Sclerotinia* [34].

Zinc complexes with antimicrobial activity

Zinc(II) complexes of carboxylates appeared to have good antibacterial activity; e.g., a strong inhibitive effect was noticed towards *E. coli* and *S. aureus* [35]. In the search for zinc(II) complexes of known antimicrobial drugs strong antibacterial activity has been achieved; e.g. the interaction between zinc and the gyrase inhibitor ciprofloxacin and various nitrogen-donor ligands have been studied and the complexes were found more potent than the drugs alone. The investigation of complexes of thiosemicarbazones gave promising results as well. A noticeable selective activity was seen by zinc(II) complexes of picolinaldehyde-S-methyl- and -S-benzylthiosemicarbazones which were active in comparison to their metal free ligands. Moreover, there zinc(II) complexes of salicylaldehyde were found active against *S. aureus* [36].

Zinc(II) complexes of sulfa drugs, such as sulfadiazine and sulfamerazine also proved to be effective antifungal agents against *Aspergillus* and *Candida* spp. Moreover, the activities of the complexes were higher than the free ligands, but lower than the drug ketoconazole. Zinc(II) complexes with amino acids have been developed with antimicrobial activity. The antibacterial activity of zinc(II) complex with S-phenylalaninato ligand was 10-fold greater than the simple metal salt. A very good inhibitory activity was also found by the yeast *Candida albicans* [34].

In general, when the antimicrobial activity of metal complexes is concerned, the following five principal factors may be considered:

- i. The chelate effect, i.e. bidentate ligands, such as the quinolones, show higher antimicrobial efficiency towards complexes with monodentate ligands
- ii. The nature of the ligands
- iii. The total charge of the complex; generally the antimicrobial efficiency decreases in the order cationic > neutral > anionic complex
- iv. The nature of the counter ion in the case of the ionic complexes
- v. The nuclearity of the metal center in the complex; binuclear centers are more active than mononuclear ones.

The antimicrobial activities of metal complexes depends more on the metal center itself than on the geometry around the metal ion [37].

CONCLUSION

After synthesis of complexes it is must to go to characterization of newly synthesized complex by different physico-chemical methods. Only one method can not reveal sufficient information alone. All information obtained from different physicochemical methods has to support one another to elucidate the structure of the complexes. In the case of antimicrobial activity complexes are more active than ligands and this reveals that metal ions have effect on normal cell process and improves the antimicrobial activity of heterocyclic ligands or any other ligands which have antimicrobial activity and coordinated with them in forming complexes. This agrees with chelation theory.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAS	Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy
BM	Bohr Magneton
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
FT-IR	Fourier Transforms Infrared
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
ppm	Parts per million
UV-Vis	Ultra Violet and Visible

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest

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